

How Cognitive Biases And Behaviors Influence Investors

Keshav Mittal

La Martiniere College, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

Human beings often undertake decisions that drive them to suboptimal results. Behavioral finance, a subfield within finance, provides an answer by contradicting the traditional assumption of rationality in financial decision-making undertaken by individual investors. It highlights the influence of cognitive and emotional biases that drive an investor into making irrational decisions, thereby earning sub-optimal results. This research essay uses the systematic review of financial literature to explore prominent behavioral biases such as overconfidence, herding, disposition, and anchoring bias and their mutual impact on investment decisions and overall market dynamics. Deriving from theoretical frameworks and studies, the essay delves into a comprehensive study of mechanisms through which these biases influence rational thinking, leading to decisions that ultimately yield underperforming outcomes and highlighting their wider impact on the financial landscape of a nation and its institutions.

Keywords: *behavioral finance, cognitive biases, overconfidence, anchoring, disposition effect, herding bias, irrationality.*

1. INTRODUCTION

People frequently do not behave rationally or as per what is required or expected of them. They deviate from the most profitable or efficient ways while deciding on things that lead them to lose on gains and earn below-par results. This occurs due to numerous psychological and emotional factors which are explored intricately in this essay. This section introduces the concept and emergence of irrationality in the process of making decisions.

1.1 Why does a human being behave irrationally?

To get an answer to this question, one needs to have a sound understanding of human behavior and its driving factors. Understanding behavior is a multi-faceted and complex course that

involves observing various mental and psychological processes that cumulatively have a significant impact on the decision-making of an individual. Numerous elements including upbringing, life experiences, environment, and cultural backgrounds influence people's behavior (Belsky & Gilovich, 1999). These factors frequently result in a phenomenon known as "cognitive biases". These are patterns or ways of thinking that might cause people to make irrational conclusions and therefore earn sub-optimal outcomes (Belsky & Gilovich, 1999). Such partialities are evident in the financial landscape and investment opportunities where the assumption of rationality and efficient use of resources is deviated from and can be easily quantified (Mittal & Shrivastava, 2016). Observing the recent cryptocurrency trends, one could interpret that the market hype was a prominent driving factor that caused many retail and individual investors to put their money on the line. This was done without having proper knowledge or sound understanding of the company's financial position, leading to abnormal market graphs (Shiller, 2000).

These cognitive biases exert a profound impact which significantly influences investment decision-making. Mittal and Shrivastava (2016) in their research had observed that retail investors often deviate from rational decision-making owing to certain deep and inherent psychological and emotional influences. For instance, an overconfident investor might ignore an in-depth analysis or fact sheet of a firm, assuming they have superior knowledge or expertise about a particular sector, industry, or segment of the market (Mittal & Shrivastava, 2016). Such behavior is caused by biases that not only affect individual financial outcomes but can also have a negative implication on broader markets. These deviations have reinforced the need for delving into behavioral finance, a field that blends psychology and finance to gain a better understanding as to why people make decisions that traditional financial theories like the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) fail to adequately explain (Mittal & Shrivastava, 2016).

The Efficient Market Hypothesis is based on the assumption that at any given point in time, investors would act rationally and that financial markets shall make use of all the available information. This assumption, therefore, is on the fact that asset prices always represent their true value (Fama, 1965). However, this does not hold apt in the real-world. By real-world observations, it can be inferred that investors frequently make use of mental shortcuts known as

heuristics to make these investment decisions (Kahneman & Tversky, 1974: 1125). Although these mental shortcuts can simplify complex problems, they also lead to errors in rationality or optimal use of resources. For example, mental accounting causes individuals to treat money differently depending on its source of origin (Thaler, 1985). A tax refund might be viewed as a bonus or freebie money and be spent on luxuries and comforts to satisfy wants whereas regular income shall be allocated to savings or investments (Thaler, 1999). This behavior which initially might not look daunting, can often lead to irrational financial decisions.

Having understood the basics of the causes of this behavior, comprehending it becomes all the more necessary. Behavioral finance provides an in-depth and exhaustive understanding of such tendencies through theories like Prospect Theory, developed by Kahneman and Tversky (1979). The Prospect Theory demonstrates that people mentally evaluate and act upon potential gains and losses differently and in an unbalanced way. Unlike traditional financial models which are known to assume that all outcomes are examined with proper logic and based on some scientific methodology or calculated probabilities, Prospect Theory reveals that losses weigh more heavily on emotions than equivalent gains (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). Taking an example from the stock market, the GameStop stock manipulation in 2021 showed how biases such as loss aversion (the fear of avoiding losses) and herding (the tendency to copy what others are doing) led thousands of small investors to hold onto or buy shares even when a fundamental analysis of the company's financials showed a contradictory picture (Shrotryia & Kalra, 2022). Thus, loss aversion is an imbalance- that compels investors to hold onto losing stocks for too long in the hope that they will recover from their dips, even when evidence and expert advice suggest otherwise. Additionally, another aspect of Prospect Theory- the certainty effect, shows that people prefer outcomes they perceive as guaranteed, even if those outcomes provide lower returns (Shrotryia & Kalra, 2022: 45).

Therefore, having gone through the biases and failure of hypothetical models, addressing and attempting to resolve these cognitive biases is all the more crucial. It will lead to improvement in both individual and market outcomes. Recognizing the influence of biases like loss aversion, overconfidence, and anchoring is the first step toward neutralizing and limiting their negative effects. By examining key psychological theories, such as Prospect Theory and heuristics, the

essay aims to provide a deeper understanding of how emotions and biases shape investment behavior in the global context.

1.2 Emergence of irrationality in the decision-making process

In their day-to-day lives, people make numerous decisions that may not seem rational. Similarly, in the field of investing individual investors often undertake choices without appropriate scientific or mathematical reasoning behind them. Often, the actions of such investors are influenced by their emotions, feelings, and psychology. Usually, they make use of mental shortcuts called heuristics and emotions like fear or greed to make decisions that appear unreasonable (Kahneman & Tversky, 1974).

Thus, to understand the emergence and implications of this irrationality among investors the use of a subfield within finance: behavioral finance is explored.

1.2.1 Behavioural Finance

Behavioral finance is a field that integrates psychology and finance to explain the impact of emotions and cognitive biases on investment decisions which may often lead to deviations from rational behavior (Belsky & Gilovich, 1999).

As per Mittal and Shrivastava (2016), behavioral finance recognizes that investors' financial decisions are deeply influenced by human psychology, leading to what is termed "quasi-rational" behavior—where individuals occasionally act irrationally leading to underutilization of resources. This quasi-rationality arises primarily from two factors:

1. The emotional range of an investor while making financial decisions.
2. Cognitive factors that drive individuals to take greater risks to avoid losses than to pursue equivalent gains.

In addition to this, Belsky and Gilovich (1999) referred to behavioral finance as “behavioral economics’ and said that “*Behavioral economics combines the twin disciplines of psychology and economics to explain why and how people make seemingly irrational or illogical decisions when they spend, invest, save, and borrow money.*”

Therefore, it could be concluded that the subfield of behavioral finance explains the prevalence of irrationalities and absurdities in the market and makes it the optimum branch to study to understand the stimuli of human behavior.

1.3 Frameworks and concepts:

Within behavioral finance, there are numerous theoretical models and frameworks. These frameworks help us understand human behavior and its causes and implications. This essay presents three prominent models which further add depth to the mechanisms within behavioral finance.

1.3.1 Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH)

Fama (1965) states that *"An 'efficient' market is defined as a market where there are large numbers of rational, profit-maximizers actively competing, with each trying to predict future market values of individual securities, and where important current information is almost freely available to all participants"*.

The Efficient Market Hypothesis is a traditional financial framework that is based on this concept of the efficient market. As per Fama (1965), there are three assumptions on which this EMH bases its fundamentals:

1. The investors base their decisions on securities on all the information at their disposal, in a rational manner.
2. If an individual investor goes out of the way and acts irrationally, the effect of such an act would be contradicted and balanced by the acts of the other investors who act rationally.
3. Even after that if such an irrationality persists, there are rational arbitrators present who nullify such irregularities in prices. This aids in ensuring that the assets reflect their true values.

However, despite the robust framework provided by the EMH, the reality, and the actual data differ from the hypothesized (Fama, 1965). This is due to a blend of psychology and emotional

influences and the impact they exert on the conscience of an investor. The EMH has been criticized for deviating from practicality and providing inaccurate results that do not align with the real world (Shrotryia & Kalra, 2022).

People, specifically individual investors, deviate from the rational choices influenced by numerous factors in reality thereby making irrational decisions. To understand why people often make such irrational decisions, Tversky and Kahneman (1981) introduced two key concepts: Prospect Theory and Heuristics. These concepts further add to the understanding of patterns that influence such decisions.

1.3.2 Prospect Theory:

The Prospect Theory was first introduced by Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky. It aims to explain how people treat gains and losses in an unbalanced manner. Prospect Theory contradicts the Efficient Market Hypothesis among other conventional financial theories. They imply that emotions frequently take precedence over rational thought.

One of the most important fundamental concepts within this Prospect Theory is Loss aversion. This concept states that people experience the pain and grievance of a loss far more than the joy of a gain of a similar amount (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). An investor who had invested \$10,000 in the market would experience a greater magnitude of sadness over a loss than happiness over a gain of the same \$10,000.

Besides this concept of loss aversion, another crucial component of Prospect Theory is the certainty effect. This effect shows that people prefer outcomes they perceive as guaranteed, even if those outcomes provide lower returns (Dhmi, 2020). Looking back at the financial crisis of 2008, many retail investors and households diverted their investments from equity and stock markets to more stable and seemingly secured options such as government bonds and securities. This was done in a bid to avoid the prevalent fluctuations and instability at that time (Shrotryia & Kalra, 2022).

1.3.3 Heuristics:

Heuristics are another framework for behavioral finance. Heuristics simply refers to the rules of thumb that seek to enable people to make quicker decisions and understand complex problems with relative ease (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). They do so by serving as mental shortcuts that aid in the decision-making process of an individual.

However, benefits exist along with certain shortcomings. They often cause systematic errors or biases in investment decisions. These shortcuts are useful in reducing the mental effort needed to process complex information. However, they sacrifice the accuracy and preciseness of decisions which leads to inaccurate results (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974).

Taking the example of the **representativeness heuristic** implies that investors base their decisions on the past trends or success of the stock. It is through these assumptions that they attempt to predict the performance of the investment in the future (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). In addition to the representativeness heuristic, there is another prominent heuristic: the **availability heuristic**. This causes an excess focus and preference for short-term trends and a disregard for those of the long-term by investors. It occurs by significantly emphasizing recent occurrences or pivotal news concerning an enterprise or industry (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974).

Besides these, the heuristics approach also leaves investors prone to cognitive effects like those of anchoring bias, where they hold their assumptions on particular points of reference, and overconfidence bias, where they overestimate their knowledge or expertise usually based on previous success, which makes them base their decisions on inaccuracies leading to such sub-optimal outcomes (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974).

Through the combined understanding and interpretation of these frameworks and concepts, we interpret that the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) presents a comprehensive theoretical framework explaining the rationality within investors. However, it also observes that its basis and assumptions do not hold in the real world. Along with this, we explore the prospect theory and heuristics that seek to answer the question of irrationality in human beings with theoretical concepts and examples.

2. DISCUSSION

As discussed earlier, biases are patterns within the human mind that can lead to irrational and consequently poor decision-making. This is specifically evident in financial matters. These biases come from mental shortcuts and personal beliefs that seem to make difficult decisions easier to comprehend but often lead to mistakes and inaccuracies (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). In the field of finance, these biases can significantly influence decision-making. They may change the way people view risk and lead to poor investment choices. For example, some investors may become overconfident and think they know better than they do (Mittal & Shrivastava, 2016). They also tend to copy others without thinking or carrying investment losses due to emotions. By understanding these biases and their subsequent effects, broader implications on investment decisions become evident. This section explains common biases such as overconfidence, anchoring, the disposition effect, and herding bias and how they affect investors and the market.

2.1 Overconfidence

Overconfidence is one of the most common biases in human beings which is highly relevant in behavioral finance. Mittal and Shrivastava (2016) state that “Overconfidence refers to the tendency of individuals to overestimate the accuracy of their knowledge and the validity of their predictions, leading them to underestimate risks and overrate their abilities”.

It is through this overestimation of abilities, that investors gain a false sense of confidence, driving them to trade excessively in an attempt to outperform the market (Mittal & Shrivastava, 2016). Taking the example of an individual investor, they may sell a stock that is performing well because based on their knowledge and belief they may expect to earn higher returns by investing the same amount elsewhere. This on the contrary could lead them to bear losses on the invested amount instead. Similarly, despite declining fundamentals, they may hold onto the stock: thinking that it would earn higher returns in the future (Odean, 1998). Thus, it could be interpreted that overconfidence brings false confidence and motivates individuals to act impulsively.

Moreover, this overconfidence does not solely affect individuals, it can also disrupt markets. Boubaker and Talbi (2013) in their paper explained that overconfidence increases market volatility. For example, if a certain stock has been delivering consistent negative returns and a rumor regarding a large deal or a profitable venture concerning the stock is spread, a certain group of investors may deem it more than appropriate and thereby overreact and hoard the stock. This would eventually lead to market disruptions and unreasonable fluctuations (Boubaker & Talbi, 2013). Besides market anomalies, overconfident investors are often those with experience or who have previously been successful. Chen et al. (2007) in their paper indicated that these investors misread information and may push up the prices of stocks based on speculation, creating market bubbles that ultimately break. Robin and Angelina (2020) added that former wins make investors overconfident and they start taking bigger risks. This more often leads to irrationality in the process and backfires.

In addition to past experiences, overconfidence can look different depending on gender as well. Studies by Boubaker and Talbi (2013) and Syarkani and Alghifari (2022) pointed out that men tend to take more risks, usually, putting all their money in one sector, like tech stocks, while women are more likely to diversify. However, overconfident investors irrespective of their demographics tend to be too dependent on their judgment. For example, instead of spreading their investments across various sectors, overconfidents might go all out on one company's stock, expecting to get enormous returns without considering the value of diversification (Boubaker & Talbi, 2013).

In summary, overconfidence is one of the most common biases that an investor may be influenced by while making investment decisions thereby making irrational choices. This feeling of excessive expertise within an investor could give rise to excessive trading, poor decision-making, and market inefficiency. All of this would cause losses to the investors involved.

2.2 Anchoring

After overconfidence, another common behavioral bias in finance is anchoring. Tversky & Kahneman (1974) states that "Anchoring refers to the tendency of individuals to rely too heavily on an initial piece of information (the 'anchor') when making decisions, even if it is irrelevant or insufficiently accurate". This was elaborated by Furnham and Boo (2011) who elucidated the concept of how a person's fixation on initial information impacts the choices that he would make later on. This has broader and more serious implications in the financial landscape.

Tversky and Kahneman (1974) showed through experiments that investors are unable to deviate from these initial points or past anchors and accidentally commit errors. Looking at the cryptocurrency boom, a lot of investors based their decisions on the worth of Bitcoin being \$60,000 previously and continued purchasing the plummeting currency despite alarming market situations. This bias of anchoring is not confined to individuals but also to disrupting financial systems. Rohatgi (2021) found that anchoring distorts valuation models and price predictions and this leads to flawed investment decisions. For example, investors might overvalue a stock based on outdated information that they still deem relevant. They do so with their past position in mind and consider their former standing worthy.

The impact of anchoring bias also varies among different groups of people. Interestingly, Owusu and Laryea (2022) in their work concluded that financially literate investors and women are more prone to this bias. This goes against the general notion of financial knowledge being vital in reducing the influence of biases. Comprehending this with the example of mutual funds, a potential investor might base their decision to invest in a fund on favorable and lucrative return graphs of the previous years, without consideration for the current market trends. This phenomenon occurs in financially literate investors due to the chances of reconsideration of past graphs while leaving little regard for present or future projections.

In addition, Furnham and Boo (2011) emphasized that personal traits also influence the intensity of an investor's anchor to their decisions. To have a sound understanding of this concept, consider a potential house buyer who is aware of a recent sale of a house similar to his

aspirations at 100,000 dollars. Then, even if the current financial conditions deviate, they might still anchor to that amount and consider it a plausible price for their bargain.

However, contrary to the assumption of anchoring a negative connotation, it might not always cause harm. Olson et al. (2014) in his paper studied herding by analyzing online prediction markets and concluded that anchoring in certain situations assists forecasters in making better predictors by using past trends as a common ground. Looking at the stock market, if a certain stock has stayed within the range of \$1,100 for certain months, then it could be used as a baseline by traders to conduct their investments. This highlights the potential of anchoring in certain situations depending on the context.

To conclude, anchoring bias also exerts a significant influence on individuals, especially in the financial context. It makes them cling to obsolete initial starting points and overly rely on them. This over-reliance which is more prominent among the financially literate leads to irrational judgements and the potential for large-scale market inefficiencies.

2.3 Disposition effect

Besides overconfidence and anchoring, another common cognitive bias in behavioral finance is the disposition effect.

As per Shefrin & Statman (1985), "The disposition effect refers to a behavioral bias where investors tend to sell assets that have gained value too early, to lock in gains, while holding onto assets that have lost value for too long, in the hope of recovery".

This irrational behavior which is occasionally exhibited by investors might seem contradictory as it bases the decisions on past performances instead of prospects. This therefore disregards the potential that the investing asset might harbor (Odean, 1998). The meaning of disposition effect is caused by the human tendency to secure repetitive gains but unable to bear losses while trading. Looking from the perspective of an individual investor, a gain of even 10% on a stock might make him overjoyed causing him to sell it impulsively. On the other hand, he might cling to another stock that has a loss of 20%, unable to bear it (Shefrin & Statman, 1985).

Further, Kahneman and Tversky (1979) in their Prospect Theory aptly explain this bias. They demonstrated how people treat losses and gains in an unbalanced manner. This makes them exhibit different behaviors at losses and gains of the same amount. For instance, if someone loses ₹500, it would feel significantly worse than the happiness of gaining ₹500 even though both are the same amount (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979).

Therefore, it is this feeling that makes investors cling to investments much longer than what is appropriate with the aspiration of future success despite its present declining situation. This aids in avoiding the emotional displeasure of realizing losses. On the contrary, investors jump onto gaining investments as they desperately wish to secure profit. This would be the case even if there is a possibility of further profits by holding it in the future (Shefrin & Statman, 1985). Adding to it, Odean (1998) studied over 10000 brokerage trading data and confirmed that this behavior is prevalent among investors which has driven them to suboptimal results and lackluster performances in their investment portfolios.

A peculiar observation about the disposition effect is that it has a different implication for different investor profiles. This was confirmed by Feng and Chau (2009) who used account-level trading data from an online brokerage in China. Through his study which involved different investor profiles from experts to novices', they concluded that amateur investors are far more susceptible to such traps as compared to experienced professionals. This therefore causes variance in the implications of disposition effect. For instance, a beginner who has just started investing may avoid trading shares at a significant loss in hopes of its recovery shortly whereas an expert might deem that existing earlier could be a superior alternative (Feng & Seasholes, 2005).

Moreover, the disposition effect does not only influence individual investors. Frazzini (2006) analyzed data from both retail and institutional investors and suggested that it has a broader implication on the dynamics of the entire market and could result in anomalies. He explained that this occurs when a large number of investors together exhibit such a disposition effect which would lead to a wider change and cause disruption of the adequate or rational forces of the

market. This would consequently lead to strange market graphs and situations where the assets do not reflect their intrinsic values. For example, if a large number of investors collectively avoid selling a certain falling stock, then it would lead to an abnormal and false price hike (Frazzini, 2006).

From the above discussion, it can be concluded that the disposition effect is another prominent cognitive bias that influences investment-making decisions largely by novice investors. This compels them to treat losses and gains differently which causes an unequal balance between their actions. This when culminated together leads to larger disruptions and irregularities in the markets making it a concern that drives irrationality and below-par returns.

2.4 Herding bias

Lastly, herding is another bias that is common among human beings. Banerjee (1992) in his work had developed the "herd behavior model". This herd behavior model showcases that such an effect arises when people act only in accord with others' actions. Banerjee suggested that although it might initially appeal as a secured investment, it could eventually lead to irrational inflation, inefficiencies, and even full-scale financial crises. Understanding this herding bias with the surge in the Indian stock market's IPOs, it could be observed that during it many renowned offerings from companies like Paytm and Zomato were subscribed irrationally solely based on the actions of their peers (Chang et al., 2000).

Bikhchandani, Hirshleifer, and Welch (1992) in their work described the formation of informational cascades as a potential reason for this herding bias. They suggested this formation to be the result of a large and sequential chain reaction within which each acts as a link by ignoring their individual beliefs and knowledge and in turn making decisions based on their peers. Another application of it in the real world was the financial crisis of 2008, numerous investors panicked by seeing the large-scale action of others. They disregarded the soundness of their holdings and sold their investments influenced by peer actions. This behavior was exhibited in a chain which caused their values to sink further. Therefore, these informational cascades demonstrate how herding causes such fluctuations and crises leading to irrationality in the process of decision-making (Bikhchandani, Hirshleifer, & Welch, 1992).

Besides large-scale crises, Chang et al. (2000) in his work found the prevalence of herding in developing and emerging markets. This is because reliable information in such markets is very limited and the financial institutions are less effective. This is common in markets such as India wherein developing institutions for sectors like real estate has led to abnormal prices and subsequent collapse of the market structures, leaving investors doomed with losses. (Chang et al., 2000)

Olson et al. (2014) argued that following peers might not always drive humans into making irrational choices. In certain situations and cases, it is this herding bias that provides stability to markets and financial institutions when the fundamentals are unclear or the dependable and tangible knowledge is limited. However such positive effects are constrained to situations wherein the crowd collectively acts on the viability and truthfulness of the information available to the crowd (Olson et al., 2014)

This behavior of herding is also influenced by the investor profile and experience. Bikhchandani, Hirshleifer, and Welch (1992) found that amateur investors are more likely to engage in herding compared to seasoned and experienced investors as they base their decisions on comprehensive independent analysis.

Therefore, herding is a human bias that makes investors follow peer actions blindly without independent analysis. This has been a catalyst for large-scale financial disasters causing market instability. Mostly followed by novice investors who lack experience, this bias may sometimes lead to positive outcomes for developing marketing that lacks proper information. All of this makes herding an important bias to deal with in behavioral finance.

3. CONCLUSION

This essay, through the systematic review of financial literature, explored the traditional financial concepts and biases. It delved into the psychological and emotional factors affecting human behavior through the means of cognitive biases. These biases are ingrained in the financial landscape, especially among the individual investors. The essay explored the causes for the

emergence of four of the most prominent biases and their implications for such investors and the broader financial markets. Overconfidence is a prominent bias that leads to excessive confidence in one's expertise leading to a disregard for fundamental analysis and expert advice. Apart from overconfidence, anchoring causes over-dependence on outdated initial points which leads to irrational decisions which make the financially aware more prone to it. Besides these two, the disposition effect makes humans treat losses and gains disproportionately leading to large irregularities in the markets. Lastly, herding behavior causes individuals to follow what others are doing, depriving them of individual analysis and interpretations, and has been the cause of major financial crises across the world. Cumulatively, these biases significantly influence the way we act and make decisions, especially in a financial context and ultimately obtain below-par results.

4. LIMITATIONS

Although the essay provided a comprehensive insight into human behavior and behavioral finance by reviewing existing financial literature, it lacks a study of primary evidence or independent research on investors. This could have added more depth and further strengthened the analysis presented. Moreover, in addition to the existing exploration of biases and their implications on the market dynamics and individual returns, there could have been an exploration of measures to mitigate the extent of their impact on the financial markets.

REFERENCES

- Banerjee, A. V. (1992). A simple model of herd behavior. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 107(3), 797–817. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/2479551>
- Belsky, G., & Gilovich, T. (1999). *Why smart people make big money mistakes*. Simon & Schuster.
- Bikhchandani, S., Hirshleifer, D., & Welch, I. (1992). A theory of fads, fashion, custom, and cultural change as informational cascades. *Journal of Political Economy*, 100(5), 992–1026. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/222536679>
- Boubaker, S., & Talbi, D. (2013). Overconfidence bias and financial market anomalies: A time series analysis. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 29, 10–18. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/256354177>
- Chang, E. C., Cheng, J. W., & Khorana, A. (2000). An examination of herd behavior in equity markets: An international perspective. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 24(10), 1651–1679. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/223581946>

- Chen, G., Kim, K. A., Nofsinger, J. R., & Rui, O. M. (2007). Trading performance, disposition effect, overconfidence bias, and experience of emerging market investors. *Journal of Behavioral Decision Making*, 20(4), 425–451. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/229493881>
- Fama, E. F. (1965). The behavior of stock-market prices. *The Journal of Business*, 38(1), 34–105. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/310101379>
- Feng, L., & Seasholes, M. S. (2005). Do investor sophistication and trading experience eliminate behavioral biases in financial markets? *Review of Finance*, 9(3), 305–351. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/4981940>
- Frazzini, A. (2006). The disposition effect and underreaction to news. *The Journal of Finance*, 61(4), 2017–2046. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228204074>
- Kahneman, D., & Tversky, A. (1979). Prospect theory: An analysis of decision under risk. *Econometrica*, 47(2), 263–292. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/239927365>
- Mittal, M., & Shrivastava, V. (2016). Behavioral factors influencing investment decision-making: A review. *International Journal of Research in Commerce & Management*, 7(6), 42–46.
- Odean, T. (1998). Are investors reluctant to realize their losses? *The Journal of Finance*, 53(5), 1775–1798. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228194347>
- Shiller, R. J. (2000). *Irrational exuberance*. Princeton University Press.
- Shrotryia, V. K., & Kalra, D. (2022). Behavioral finance: Understanding biases and improving investment decisions. *Journal of Financial Studies and Research*, 14(3), 35–55